

A Study on Stock Price Behavior and Forecasting of Selected Indian Companies Stock Using Technical Analysis

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Abstract

Technical analysis is a study of the stock market relating to factors affecting demand and supply of stocks and also helps in understanding, the intrinsic value of shares whether the shares are undervalued and overvalued. The stock market indicators would help the investor to identify the major increasing and decreasing trend in share price movements, thus the signal helps the investor to indentify the market. Thus technical analysis as a tool which helps the investor to understand the market whether to buy or sell the share price at a particular point of time though it is fundamentally strong. The objective of the present study is to make a study on stock price behavior and forecasting of selected Indian companies stock using technical analysis. The study purely based on secondary data which includes the historical data available from the website. For the purpose of analysis techniques used for the study is Beta, relative strength index and moving average convergence and divergence to know the stock of the company's shares are technically strong. On the basis of the analysis the paper concludes one can buy stock of Asian paints, Bharti Airtel, ITC which are technically strong to get good amount of return in near future and in Reliance and Hindustan Unilever the investors can sell or hold position of scrip for future.

Keywords: Technical analysis, Scrip value, prediction of securities, convergence and divergence. **JEL Classification:** JEL: E3, JEL: E2, JEL: E37

Introduction

Today, many people are getting aware about stock market and large numbers of people are investing their surplus amount in shares of the company to get good amount of returns from stocks but at the same time they have to bear risk of fluctuations in earnings due to volatility. So as to minimize the effect of risk various theories and modules had been formulated, among them this paper is formulated with technical analysis. Technical Analysis is the forecasting of future financial price movements based on an examination of past price movements of the market by using technical indicators like graphs, charts and oscillators. Naturally all investors would like their

investments to appreciate rapidly in price which may satisfy their wish and tend to be accomplished by a greater amount of risk and many investors are not willing to accept. However it is important to understand that investors can be very conscious about the stock price movements. Companies listed in NSE top movers is selected for the study and which helps the investors to understand the intrinsic value of shares and to know whether the shares are overvalued or undervalued. It becomes essential to know the performance and the investors will be duly giving returns and ensures safety of the investment. Thus the strength of the analysis depends on how accurately the price movements are predicted.

Review of literature

Bhardwaj, Raheja and Priyanka (2012)¹ examined two oscillators the moving average convergence and divergence (MACD) and relative strength index (RSI) to see if these rules were profitable. It was the longest UK index and the sample period is from July 1995 to January 1994. Daily closing prices within this period were adopted for analysis. It is found that the RSI as well as MACD can generate higher return than the buy and hold strategy.

Milos Stojanovic (2015)² this paper examines the efficiency of technical analysis and predicting modelling in defining the optimal strategy for investing in stock market. This paper uses technical indicators such as MACD, RSI etc. The paper concludes that machine learning techniques capture non linear models adequately and these model performers buy and hold strategy in maximization of profitability on investment.

Statement of the Problem

Investment timing plays a crucial role in share market. In recent days the market goes on declining trend because of depreciating money value and ILFS Debt crisis the investors, analysts face difficulties in choosing the correct forecasting of a company share. Predicting share movements is difficult especially when the market is highly volatile. Investors are required making entry and exit strategy in order to make profit and avoid losses. Hence this study is taken up in order to use technical indicators and suggests the investors to decide which share to buy or sell strategies return and risk analysis.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyze the share price movements and forecast the trends in selected company stock.
2. To examine the risk and return of selected company stock.

Research Methodology

The study aims at analyzing the price movements of selected company stock. The study is on descriptive and analytical in nature. For technical analysis daily share price movements are analyzed for 3 months from 1-october-2018 to 4-january-2019. The closing prices of share prices were taken and the future price movement was analyzed by using secondary data like article, journal to analysis the performance of company share price and financial tools are been used. Random sampling has been used to select the companies which are top most five companies listed with NSE before ILFS crisis after the recovery of the crisis the companies are in high fluctuation so these companies are selected to analyze the impact of ILFS crisis on their market volatility. The selected companies are:

1. Asian paints
2. Bharti Airtel
3. Reliance

4. ITC
5. Hindustan Unilever

Tools and Techniques used in this study are:

1. BETA
2. Moving average convergence and divergence
3. Relative strength index
4. Standard deviation

BETA

BETA factor describes the movement in a stock’s or a portfolio’s returns in relation to that of the market return. The main purpose of using beta is to predict the change in the market. Beta is a measure of the market or non-diversible risk associated with any given security in the market. The formula for predicting Beta is as follows:

Market value of Beta= $\frac{P1-P0}{P0} \times 100$

Where P1 today’s closing price, P0 previous closing price

The analysis is done based on the following rule:

- If the beta is 1= The share’s movement will be along with the market
- If the beta value is >1 = the share’s movement will be more volatile than the market.
- If the beta value is <1 = the share’s movement will be less volatile than the market.

Analysis and Interpretation

Asian Paints

The BETA value is 2.89 more than, the stock is more volatile than the market. If the market rise or falls by 1% then the stock would outperform or underperform respectively.

Chart 1
Moving Average Convergence and Divergence and Relative Strength Index
October 2018-December 2018

In RSI analysis the company performance, the company share price is in oversold region in the month of October and November which goes on upward trend in movement of shares till December, and the price goes on decreasing for the first week of January thus the company share price indicates overbought condition to the investors. In moving average analysis, the moving average price of the shares goes upward and downward and the price is fluctuation before December and the investor may not able to buy or sell the share thus the investor has to hold the share, then there is sudden increases and goes up and price line till 89.45 per share this indicate buying signal for the investor.

Bharti Airtel

The Beta value is 0.982 less than 1, the scrip is less volatile than the market. It is less risky to invest in this company.

Chart 2
Moving Average Convergence and Divergence and Relative Strength Index
October 2018-December 2018

In RSI analysis the company share closes in oversold condition and goes upward trend in the month of November and it shows positive note that the prices may increases in future. Thus the market shows bullish signal for the investor to buy the shares and hold for the future. The MACD analysis, the moving average goes on fluctuation trend and the market is volatile, when the volatility increases, risk increases and returns decreases and the price line indicates buying signal for the investor.

Reliance industries

The Beta value is 1.09 approximately equal to 1 the share movement along with the market and it will affect the scrip.

Chart 3
Moving Average Convergence and Divergence and Relative Strength Index
October 2018-December 2018

In RSI analysis, the company price goes on downward trend and it shows overbought condition, and there is slight variation after December and the trend line goes up and there is an opportunity to increase the market price in future and the investor buy the shares and get good amount of return in future. In moving average analysis, the price line is fluctuating and goes on down trend for the past two months from November to January and it indicates bearish market thus the price line shows selling signal for the investor.

ITC

The beta value is 0.169 less than 1; it shows that the scrip is less volatile than the market and it is less risky to invest in this company.

Chart 4
Moving Average Convergence and Divergence and Relative Strength Index
October 2018-December 2018

In RSI analysis, there is a slight variation in the company share price and it does not reflect more on ITC thus the company is in oversold condition, thus the price will increase in future. In moving average analysis the MACD price line goes on increasing trend till end of December and closing price of the company share is fluctuating in the first week of January and the price line determines to buy the share which gives actual return on investment or it will tend to give good amount of return, it will not give loss to the investor, thus the investor can wait and buy the share.

Hindustan Unilever

The BETA value is 1.4 and it is approximately equal to 1 thus the investor can invest but the prediction of future may not be fixed.

Chart 5
Moving Average Convergence and Divergence and Relative Strength Index
October 2018-December 2018

In RSI analysis the company share price goes upward trend in all the month of the study, it shows positive signal in the month of December and tends to increase in near future, so the investor gets more profit of their investment. In moving average analysis the MACD shows on fluctuating trend and goes on decreasing after December, thus the price line indicates that the share has to sell at a maximum price where the investor can get away from loss.

Suggestions

- The investors may go for the buying decision because the prices are high in Asian Paints and Bharti Airtel, ITC.
- The investor may go for the selling decision because the price goes down and in Reliance and Hindustan Unilever.
- The investor can hold the shares till March 2018 in Asian Paints, Bharti Airtel and ITC may reach 42%, 28% and 31% return in near future.

- Investor can invest their money Asian Paints, Bharati Airtel, Hindustan and ITC companies market price and net profit are increasing at higher rate than Reliance and Bharti Airtel. Investors must also take into account various factors like government of India budget, company performance, political and social events before any decision is made. The future returns should be fundamentally good, therefore it is advisable for the investor to make technical analysis of stocks for better return on investments.

Conclusion

From the above analysis it can be concluded that the stock market is very volatile and it is solely dependent on the pattern of investment by the investor. The investor can lose large amount of savings and to minimize the impact of risk, thus technical analysis can be used as a tool to predict the future price movements whether to buy or sell and to gain maximum profit in future. Therefore proper decision should be made by the investor otherwise they will lose their unnecessary amount of investment.

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